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PSYCHO-SOCIAL VARIABLES AS PREDICTORS OF CHEATING TENDENCY AMONG STUDENTS IN CALABAR EDUCATIONAL ZONE

D. O. IDIKA and M. T. JOSHUA

ABSTRACT

The study was designed to investigate some psycho-social variables as predictors of students' tendency to cheat in examination. Specifically, the study examined the extent to which socio-economic status, study habit, achievement motivation, test anxiety, self concept and attribution to hard work, when taken together, would predict students' tendency to cheat in examination, and the relative contribution of each of these variables to the prediction of students' cheating tendency. A sample of 600 Senior Secondary School students (300 males and 300 females) from ten secondary schools in five local government areas in Calabar Educational Zone, Cross River State, Nigeria was drawn using stratified random sampling. A questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The reliability estimates of sub-scales measuring psycho-social variables ranged from 0.76 to 0.93, with overall reliability of 0.87, while the reliability estimate of the sub-scale measuring the dependent variable was 0.95. Multiple regression analysis was carried out to determine the joint and individual contributions of the six psycho-social (independent) variables to the prediction of students' cheating tendency in examination. The result showed that the psycho-social variables, when taken together significantly predicted students' tendency to cheat in examination. The psycho-social variables jointly explained 57.2% of the variance in the dependent variable. However, when examined individually, five of the six independent variables (with the exception of study habit) were found to be significant predictors of cheating tendency. It was recommended that teachers and counsellors should identify strategies of reducing anxiety among students.

KEYWORDS: Examination, Cheat, Calabar Educational Zone, Psycho-social, Study habit

INTRODUCTION

In every educational system, tests/examinations have been the major evaluative tools for ascertaining the effectiveness of instruction and students' learning. Such evaluation is expected to give a correct level of attainment and competence, which invariably forms major requirements for job placements and admission into institutions of higher learning. As a result, students have come to see examinations and tests as a 'war' of survival, and cheating as effective means of survival (Isangedighi, 1986). Cheating is a deviance, a behaviour that violates the standards of conduct or expectations of a group or society (Wickman, 1991). It is a deviation from the societal norms and values. Isangedighi (1989) views cheating as a deliberate act of commission made by a candidate alone, or jointly with others, in order to obtain a grade that is better than he is capable of obtaining. Tendency to cheat involves individual's intentional and unfair urge to get a score higher than what his ability and honest effort in the subject would have otherwise enabled him.

In Nigeria, the tendency of students to cheat in examinations and actual examination malpractices have remained major disciplinary problems in our schools that have continued to attract the attention of professional counsellors, educators, administrators, examining bodies and researchers. Denga and Denga (1998) have observed that this problem has become a sustained social virus that is rapidly acquiring the status of a social and educational epidemic in Nigeria. It has continued to threaten the credibility of the certificates issued by the examining bodies. Solutions therefore to the problem of cheating must be proffered, and quickly too, if education must keep its efficacy and strength.

Emerging literature on examination malpractice indicate that examination malpractice is neither new nor peculiar to Nigeria. The dishonest act has been a worldwide phenomenon subtly exhibited in different parts of the world. Cheating in examination was recorded to have occurred in Nigeria as far back as 1914 (Adeyegbe & Oke, 1994, Maduemezia, 1998).

Cheating behaviours have been known to manifest in many forms, such as: bringing in foreign materials (pieces of

paper, notes, textbooks, handkerchiefs, programmable calculators, skirts, waist slips, currency notes, photocopies of prepared answers, and dangerous weapons) Candidates copy their preparatory notes on these materials which are too personal for any body to suspect. Other forms include irregular activities inside or outside the examination hall, such as, use of mathematical set, log tables, rulers and calculators and recently, handsets to exchange information. The rate of students' involvement in it, however, has tended to be on the increase as the years go by (Idika, 2005). Hardly any year passes that one board or another has not been constituted to investigate and find lasting solutions to this problem.

Newspaper reports (Guardian 1995 Oct 28 p 4 and Punch 2002, Aug 17, p 35 & 38) of rampant incidence of withholding of external examination results and the punishing of students for various kinds of examination malpractices overwhelmingly testify to the prevalence of cheating with modified innovations during examinations in Nigerian schools.

Cheating in examinations at the secondary school level has undermined people's fate in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) and this has brought despair to many families. Several results of innocent students have been withheld. There have been cases of cancellation of results. Some schools have been blacklisted as examination centres because of examination fraud. Other consequences of the unethical behaviour of examination cheating are loss of self-confidence on the part of students; poor attitude to studies, loss of honesty and integrity by students, loss of trust in the entire examination system by the society (Adebayo, 1996).

In an attempt to curb the problem of cheating, the federal government has over the years instituted commissions of inquiry acted upon the commissions' findings and recommendations, introduced legislations and decrees, ranging from withholding and cancellation of results to imprisonment. Despite these measures, the problem of cheating has remained intractable. In a situation of this nature, therefore, it becomes imperative to look beyond punishment and other measures as a means of correcting this dishonest behaviour, to a more lasting and enduring solution, perhaps through social action research.

While there exists a considerable literature on examination malpractice/cheating tendency among students, much is yet to be done on psycho-social correlates of cheating tendency. Moreover, few related studies (like Denga, 1983; Ali, 1986; Isanghedighi, 1986, 1989; Enu, 2001; Agbor, 2004) considered factors like gender, socio economic background and family variables as possible determinants or predictors. Besides, these studies relied on statistical techniques such as chi-square, which revealed only bivariate relations. Based on these the present study was designed to investigate some psycho-social variables as predictors of students' tendency to cheat in examination. The purpose of this study was therefore to examine the extent to which some psycho-social variables - parental socio-economic status, study habit, achievement motivation, test anxiety, self concept and attribution to hard work - when taken together, would predict students' tendency to cheat in examination, and the relative contribution of each of the variables to the prediction of students' cheating tendency.

METHODOLOGY

Subjects: Subjects were 600 Senior Secondary School students (300 males and 300 females) selected from ten secondary schools in five local government areas (LGAs) in Calabar, Cross River State, through stratified random sampling. Two schools were randomly selected from each LGA. Their age range was 15-19 years with a mean of 16.6 and standard deviation of 6.7. In each school that participated in the study, sixty students were randomly selected from senior secondary classes 1, 2 and 3 to give a total of 600 students.

Twenty students (10 males and 10 females) were selected from each of SS1, SS2 and SS3 classes. **Instrument:** A questionnaire on psycho-social variables, and tendency to cheat, was used for data collection. The questionnaire comprised seven sub scales in accordance with the six psycho-social variables and the dependent variable (cheating tendency). Apart from the subscale that dealt with socio-economic status, items in all other subscales of the questionnaire were of Likert type, with four response categories of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Face validity and content validity were determined for the questionnaire using two experts in Educational measurement and Evaluation. The reliability estimates for the six sub-scales of psycho-social variables ranged from 0.76, to 0.93, with overall reliability of 0.87, while the reliability of the sub-scale measuring the dependent variable was 0.95. These estimates, which were determined by split-half reliability method, and which are measures of internal consistency, were considered appropriate to justify the use of the instrument for the study.

Procedure for Data analysis: Simultaneous multiple regression analysis (i.e "enter" option) was carried out to determine the joint and relative contributions of the six psycho-social variables to the prediction of students' cheating tendency in examination.

RESULTS

The intercorrelations among the seven variables of the study are shown in Table 1; while the results of the multiple regression analysis are shown in Table 2. The intercorrelations are significant at .05 probability level. This shows that there are significant relationships among the variables studied.

TABLE 1 Matrix of intercorrelations among the seven study variables

Variable	Socio-economic status	Study habit	Achievement motivation	Self-concept	Test anxiety	Attribution to hard work	Tendency to cheat
Socio-economic status	1.00	.287	.372	.328	.397	.398	.449
Study habit	.287	1.00	.554	.463	.399	.427	.465
Achievement motivation	.372	.554	1.00	.509	.462	.542	.562
Self-concept	.328	.463	.509	1.00	.562	.572	.611
Test anxiety	-.397	-.399	-.462	.562	1.00	.479	.605
Attribution to hard work	.398	.427	.542	.572	-.479	1.00	.608
Tendency to Cheat	-.449	-.465	-.562	-.611	.605	-.608	1.00

TABLE 2 Results of multiple regression analysis of predicting tendency to cheat using six psycho-social variables

Multiple R	=	757
Multiple R Square (R) ²	=	572
Adjusted Multiple R Square	=	568
Standard Error of Estimate	=	4 61

Source of variation	sum of squares	df	Mean square	F
Regression	16842 433	6	2807 072	132 25*
Residual	12586 740	593	21 226	
Total	29429 173	599		

Variables	Unstd. Reg. Wts. (b)	Std. Reg. Wts(β)	SEB	t-ratio	P-level
Scio-econ status	- 851	- 126	021	-4.131	.000*
Study habit	- 148	.064	.078	-1.890	0.59
Achievement motivation	- 287	- 144	.073	-9.47	.000*
Self-concept	- 339	- 205	.061	-5.537	.000*
Test anxiety	.388	.243	.055	6.996	.000*
Attribution to hard work	- 433	- 219	.071	-6.063	.000*

*p<.01 (Critical F_{6,593} = 2. 12; Critical t = 2.576)

Table 2 shows that a combination of the psycho-social variables (parental socio-economic status, study habit, achievement motivation, self concept, test anxiety, and attribution to hard work) in predicting students' cheating tendency in examination yielded a multiple correlation coefficient (R) of .757 and hence R-square (R²) of .572. This implies that the psycho-social variables jointly explained or predicted 57.2% of the variance in the dependent variable. The table also shows that analysis of variance for the multiple regression data produced an F-ratio of 132.254, which is significant at .01 level. This implies that the psycho-social variables, when taken together are significant predictors of students' tendency to cheat in examination.

As can be seen in Table 2, the standardized regression weights (β) ranged from .064 to .243, unstandardized regression weights (b) ranged from -851 to .388, standard error of estimate ranged from .021 to .78 and t-ratio from -6.063 to 6.996. The t-ratios for five variables (parental socio-economic status, achievement motivation, self concept, test anxiety and attribution to hard work) were significant at .01 level. The t-ratio for study habit was not significant at .05 probability level. This result implies that five of the six psycho-social variables (with exception of study habit) when taken individually, significantly predict students' cheating tendency in examination. On the basis of the standardized regression weights (β), the result further shows that test anxiety makes the highest contribution to cheating tendency, followed by attribution to hard work, self concept, achievement motivation and then parental socio-economic status in that order. The negative β value shows a reciprocal causation between the variables involved. Path analysis seeks to decompose the total correlation into direct and indirect components. β is a direct component of the total correlation.

The β value for each of the variables expresses the change in students' cheating tendency due to a unit change in the particular variable when the other psycho-social variables are kept constant. From Table 2, a unit change in the test anxiety of the students will lead to a .243 change in students' cheating tendency. However, in the negative direction, attribution to hard work made the greatest contribution to students' cheating tendency with a value of -.219, followed by

self concept - .205, then achievement motivation - .144 and socio economic status with a coefficient of -.126, in that order. Study habit generally made the least contribution to students' cheating tendency in examination with β = .064, which was not statistically significant at .05 level.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of multiple regression analysis revealed that the six psycho-social variables (parental socio-economic status, study habit, achievement motivation, self-concept, test anxiety and attribution to hard work) when taken together are significant predictors of cheating tendency among students who participated in this study. The observed F-ratio of 132.25 was significant at .01 level, indicating that the effectiveness of a joint contribution of the psycho-social variables in predicting students' cheating tendency could not have occurred by chance. The magnitude of the relationship between the students' tendency to cheat in examination and the independent variables is reflected in the values of coefficients of multiple correlation (R) of .757 and multiple correlation square (R²) of .572. Thus, the results reveal that the psycho-social variables when taken together accounted for 57.2% of the total variance in the students' cheating tendency.

The values of t-ratios associated with the psycho-social variables showed that five variables (parental socio-economic status, self-concept, achievement motivation, test anxiety and attribution to hard work) out of the six psycho-social variables contributed significantly to the prediction of students' cheating tendency. This result tends to support the earlier findings of Biehler (1978), Ali (1986), Nenty (1985, 1988 & 1989), Nyenti (1991), Ugwuegbu (1975), Jersild (1978), although these reports run contrary to that of Udom (1986). For instance, Biehler (1978) found a significant positive relationship between academic self-concept and students' tendency to cheat in examination, while Udom (1986) observed that there was a significant relationship between attribution to hard work and students' tendency to cheat in examination. Udom (1986) also reported that there was no significant relationship between test anxiety and students' tendency to cheat in examination. In spite of the inconsistent

results, socio economic status of parents affects attitude to schoolwork and support from parents

Judging from the evidence in Table 2 test anxiety made the most significant contribution to the prediction of students' cheating tendency. One possible explanation of this finding, perhaps, is the attitude of most high-test anxious students towards public examination. Nwana (1975) and Isangedighi (1986) noted that students with heightened anxiety approach examinations and tests with all amount of tension and confrontation, and in order to survive the "war", cheating technically becomes the most effective tool. Moreso, Thompson (1982) noted that the basis for many of the antisocial behaviours such as cheating among students is anxiety or feeling of alienation and that this often manifests in the form of worries and fears of failure particularly by those with poor academic records as they assume that cheating would help them achieve higher.

In interpreting the positive relationship between test anxiety and tendency to cheat, Nenty (1985) associated test anxiety with society-related factors, such factors as peer influence, pressure and expectations from home and schools as well as the general societal emphasis on certificates which exert influence on students at one time or the other, causing them to manifest the tendency to cheat. Again Nenty (1988) noted that pressure to succeed from parents relates directly and significantly with students' tendency to cheat. In line with this, Piaget as quoted by Maier (1978) concluded that such anxiety creating conditions of undue emphasis on competition and on examination grades as evidence of academic competence by the school system compel students to exhibit cheating behaviour in order to meet up with the acceptable standard.

The significant high negative relationship found between students' academic self concept and their tendency to cheat in examination implying that the higher the students' academic self-concept, the lower their tendency to cheat, was a confirmation of earlier study of Enu (2001). According to him, students with low self-esteem, less bright and low averages, tended to cheat more than their counterparts with high esteem and higher intelligence and grade averages. The result of negative β value in the self concept of students in relation to cheating tendency is further confirmed by Ukpogon (1997) that individuals who feel uncomfortable about their abilities rarely succeed in school. In order to avert the embarrassment of failure, such students may devise alternative measure of succeeding even if the measure involves cheating.

High negative β value of attribution to hard work in this study could be an indication that students readily point at factors external to them as reasons for their tendency to cheat in examination. Internal attribution reduces the tendency to cheat as students' acceptance of failure due to inadequate effort and or inability to perform helps to stimulate action in a positive direction. On the other hand, external attribution may increase the tendency to cheat. It is pertinent to note that luck and task difficulty are not within the control of the testee, they are external, and are under the control of the examiner. Therefore, a student with an external orientation would expend a greater period of his study scheming for the likely questions he/she may luckily find in an examination rather than studying intensively. When it becomes obvious that such questions are not forth coming, measures to avert the embarrassment of failure become the best alternative.

The result of significant high negative contribution of attribution to hard work in relation to anxiety and tendency to cheat derives support from the findings of Ekpe (1985) and Nenty (1989) who found significant difference in the attributional pattern of high and low anxious students. Those who attributed their performance to luck and task difficulty (external factors), exhibited a higher level of anxiety and greater tendency to cheat than those who attributed their

performance to ability and effort (internal factors) as the latter exhibited better attitude to study, less tendency to cheat in examinations, lower test anxiety and better performance in examination.

The finding that study habit is not a significant predictor of students' cheating tendency is not only unexpected, but also surprising as it contradicts the opinions and findings of many scholars including those of Asagwara (1994) and Isangedighi and Onyejiaku (1989), as quoted in Asagwara (1994), who observed significant relationship between study habit and students' cheating tendency in examination. Common sense suggests that more effective study habit should lead to more confidence during examination and therefore to less tendency to cheat. It is therefore surprising that this variable showed no significant relationship with students' cheating tendency in examination. However, it may be reasoned that the dynamic nature of human beings may have produced the difference in the result of the previous studies and this work. Secondly the unexpected result could be attributable to the sample size and the nature of population used by the different studies. The sample size used by the previous studies may have been larger or smaller than the one used in this study. Moreso, the technique of selecting the sample may not be a reflector of population characteristics. Further studies are therefore required to confirm the findings of this study with respect to the variable – study habit

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of these findings, cheating tendency can be explained with variables that surround the students. Of the six psycho-social variables studied: parental socio-economic status, study habit, achievement motivation, academic self-concept, test anxiety and attribution to hard work, test anxiety and attribution to hard work had the most significant influence on students' tendency to cheat in examination while the least influence came from the study habit.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of this study, the following recommendations would be very useful in reducing cheating tendency among students in examinations.

1. Teachers and counselors should identify strategies of reducing anxiety among students during school and external examinations by encouraging and perfecting continuous assessment or periodic examination method as is done presently in most schools in Nigeria.
2. Since some moderate level of anxiety facilitates general effectiveness, teachers therefore should identify and apply conducive and controllable anxiety situations that encourage learning by the students. This could be done through counselling services at home, schools and by other agencies.
3. Parents and teachers should consciously tackle the menace of cheating through role modeling, counselling and training of the young adolescents on the implications of antisocial behaviour such as cheating.
4. The society should restructure its values and goals. Success without effort and hard work must not be applauded or recognized.
5. Teachers should interact with students at the individual level to identify maladjustment patterns and deficiencies that tend to trigger cheating in examinations, and provide relevant counselling or therapy to check such tendencies. A workable behavioural counselling strategy that will stand the test of time should be designed to counter cheating at all levels of our school system.

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